

Synthesis and Biological Activities of Some New 2-(N-Arylamino)-4-(Fluoroaryl) thiazoles

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Twentyone new 2-(N-arylamino)-4-(fluoroaryl) thiazoles have been synthesized by the condensation of the appropriate arylthiourea with corresponding fluorophenacyl bromide in ethanol. These new compounds have been characterized by elemental analyses and spectral studies. Some representative compounds have been screened for various biological activities viz. insecticidal, virucidal, bactericidal, fungicidal, herbicidal and antiarthritic.

A number of compounds containing thiazole nucleus have been found to possess herbicidal¹⁻⁴, fungicidal⁵⁻⁸, bactericidal⁹⁻¹¹, virucidal¹²⁻¹⁴, and parasiticidal^{15,16} activities. Joshi *et al.*¹⁷ have also reported some fluorinated thiazoles as potent pesticidal agents. It is well known that introduction of fluorine atom or fluorine containing groups into the organic compounds, modify the biological activities of the compounds.

In continuation of our earlier work on fluorine containing condensed thiazoles^{18,19}, we now report the synthesis and spectral characterization of twentyone new 2-(N-arylamino)-4-(fluoroaryl) thiazoles. These fluorine containing thiazoles have been synthesized by the condensation of arylthiourea with fluorophenacyl bromide and some representative compounds have been screened for various biological activities.

Experimental

Preparation of fluorinated arylhydrocarbons :

Fluorobenzene, *o*-fluorotoluene, *m*-fluorotoluene, *p*-fluorotoluene, *o*-fluoroanisole, *m*-chlorofluorobenzene and *o*-chlorofluorobenzene were prepared from corresponding aromatic amines by the use of Balz-Schiemann reaction²⁰.

Preparation of fluorinated arylketones :

4-Fluoroacetophenone, 4-fluoro-3-methylacetophenone, 4-fluoro-2-methylacetophenone, 2-fluoro-5-methylacetophenone, 3-fluoro-4-methoxyacetophenone, 2-chloro-4-fluoroacetophenone and 3-chloro-4-fluoroacetophenone were prepared by the method of Buu-Hoi *et al.*²¹

Preparation of fluorinated phenacyl bromides :

4-Fluorophenacyl bromide, 4-fluoro-3-methylphenacyl bromide, 4-fluoro-2-methylphenacyl bromide, 2-fluoro-5-methylphenacyl bromide, 3-fluoro-4-methoxyphenacyl bromide, 2-chloro-4-fluorophenacyl bromide and 3-chloro-4-fluorophenacyl bromide were prepared by the bromination of corresponding acetophenone in chloroform/glac. acetic acid according to the literature methods²²⁻²⁴.

Preparation of 2-(N-arylamino)-4-(fluoroaryl) thiazoles :

These thiazoles were prepared by following methods :
(A) A mixture of fluorinated acetophenone (0.1 mole), thiourea (0.2 mole) and iodine (0.1 mole) was mixed together and the slurry formed was heated on a water bath for 60 hrs²⁴. It was cooled and kept in contact with ether for 24 hrs. The ether was removed and the residue washed several times with 10% hypo solution followed by water. The residue was boiled with water

Ar = fluorophenyl or a derivative

X = Cl, Br, OMe, OEt, 2', 3'-Benzo -

Scheme - I

TABLE I - CHARACTERISTIC AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 2-(N-ARYLAMINO)-4-(FLUOROARYL)THIAZOLES*

Sl. No.	Substituents in Ar	X	Molecular formula	Yield %	M. P. °C	Sulphur Calcd.	% Found	Nitrogen Calcd.	% Found
1.	4-F	4-Br	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrFN ₂ S	42.0	131	9.17	9.23	8.02	8.11
2.	4-F	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ OS	59.0	185-6	10.17	10.09	8.91	8.83
3.	4-F	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ FN ₂ OS	68.5	118	10.68	10.53	9.33	9.37
4.	4-F	2',3'-Benzo	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ FN ₂ S	24.3	180	10.01	10.12	8.74	8.69
5.	4-F, 3-CH ₃	4-Br	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ S	30.0	170	8.82	8.92	7.71	7.60
6.	4-F, 3-CH ₃	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ FN ₂ OS	45.0	143	9.76	9.90	8.53	8.48
7.	4-F, 3-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ OS	40.5	118	10.17	10.21	8.91	8.90
8.	4-F, 2-CH ₃	4-Br	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ S	60.0	144-5	8.82	8.77	7.71	7.78
9.	4-F, 2-CH ₃	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ FN ₂ OS	54.5	198	9.76	9.79	8.53	8.50
10.	4-F, 2-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ OS	58.0	87	10.17	10.11	8.91	8.87
11.	2-F, 5-CH ₃	4-Br	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ S	36.0	110	8.82	8.93	7.71	7.76
12.	2-F, 5-CH ₃	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ FN ₂ OS	50.0	123	9.76	9.67	8.53	8.47
13.	2-F, 5-CH ₃	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ OS	58.0	136	10.17	10.10	8.91	8.85
14.	2-F, 5-CH ₃	2',3'-Benzo	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ FN ₂ S	24.0	183	9.58	9.47	8.37	8.39
15.	3-F, 4-OCH ₃	4-Br	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ OS	86.0	126	8.45	8.32	7.38	7.42
16.	3-F, 4-OCH ₃	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O ₂ S	78.5	170	9.30	9.43	8.13	8.07
17.	3-F, 4-OCH ₃	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂ S	85.0	100-1	9.70	9.63	8.48	8.39
18.	2-Cl, 4-F	4-Br	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrClFN ₂ S	40.0	174	8.35	8.37	7.30	7.34
19.	2-Cl, 4-F	4-Cl	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ FN ₂ S	13.2	165	9.45	9.44	8.26	8.23
20.	3-Cl, 4-F	4-Br	C ₁₅ H ₉ BrClFN ₂ S	47.1	177	8.35	8.30	7.30	7.21
21.	3-Cl, 4-F	4-Cl	C ₁₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ FN ₂ S	10.6	168	9.45	9.38	8.26	8.29

* All these thiazoles were characterized by IR spectral studies and important characteristics absorption bands (ν_{max} in cm⁻¹) are given below ^{27,28} :

1. 3477-3250 (due to NH stretching) ; 2. 1690-1475 (due to conjugated cyclic -C=C-N=C- system) ;
3. 1300-1150 (due to Ar_{C-F} stretching) ; 4. 1140-1050 (due to 2,4-distributed thiazole ring deformation vibrations).

and filtered and the filtrate made alkaline with conc. NH₄OH yielding a solid mass, which was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol (95%). Compound Nos. 4,14,19,21 (Table 1) were prepared by using iodine and 18 & 20 by using bromine as the condensing agent (Scheme-I).

(B) A mixture of thiourea (0.02 mole) and fluorinated phenacyl bromide (0.02 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 8 hrs. with occasional shakings on water bath²⁵. After cooling, the precipitated solid was collected and then suspended in water-methanol mixture. Upon treatment with ammonia, it liberated free base, which was recrystallized from ethanol (Scheme-I).

Biological Activities :

Compound No. 1 : It showed 100% fungicidal activity against *Botrytis cinerea* at 1200 ppm concentration. However, the activity was diminished to 0% at 600 ppm.

Compound No. 3 : It was found 100% active at 1200 ppm and 75% active at 600 ppm against *B. cinerea*.

Compound No. 5 : It displayed 100% activity against *B. cinerea* at 1200 ppm.

Compound No. 6 : This compound was found to possess herbicidal activity. Pigweed was destroyed

before its emergence from the earth to the extent of 40% and 30% at the rate of 8 lbs and 4 lbs per acre, respectively. However, after the emergence, the compound was 99% active at the rate of 8 lbs per acre. Against velvet leaf, it was 98% active before emergence at 8 lbs per acre. Wild mustard was also destroyed by this compound before emergence to the extent of 100% and 98% at the rate of 8 lbs and 4 lbs per acre, respectively.

Compound No. 7: It was 100% and 50% active at 1200 ppm and 600 ppm concentrations, respectively against *B. cinerea*.

Compound No. 15: It was also 100% active at 1200 ppm against *B. cinerea*. At 600 ppm the activity became zero.

Compound Nos. 9, 13, 16 and 17 did not show activity.

Antiarthritic Activity: **Compound No. 3** was tested for antiarthritic activity, produced by a single intradermal injection of 0.75 mgs of *M. butyricum* in white paraffin oil into left food-pad of the male rats. The inflammation caused by induced arthritis at the injected site remained unaffected. However, the inflammation produced at the non-injected sites was decreased and the body weight of the animals was maintained.

Compound No. 10 was administered at a dose of 50 mgs/kg of the body weight of the male rats and its effects were observed. The animal appeared normal on the day of administration after 24 hours and after seven days.

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